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ADMINISTRATIVE MANAGEMENT AND MECHANISMS OF ITS DEVELOPMENT

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Балан О.С. Адміністративний менеджмент та механізми його розвитку.

В статті висвітлено механізм розвитку адміністративного менеджменту та досліджено вплив засобів адміністративного менеджменту на окремі його методи з метою прийняття управлінських рішень. Досліджено етапи покращення функціонування адміністративного менеджменту.

Ключові слова: адміністративний менеджмент, методи, механізм, розвиток

Balan O.S. Administrative management and mechanisms of its development.

The article outlines the mechanism of administrative management development and investigates the influence of administrative management tools on its individual methods for the purpose of making managerial decisions. The stages of improving the functioning of administrative management are investigated.

Keywords: administrative management, methods, mechanism, development

Administrative management as a science has begun to develop since the XVIII century. There are a number of theories of administrative management and the stages of its origin from ancient times to the present.

Analysis of recent researches and publications

The researchers highlighted approaches to the development of administration's theory (in particular, M. Meskon and his managerial, systemic, procedural and systemic approaches), the followers of Meskon developed a scientific opinion from the point of administrative management's view, quantitative methods, human behavior and management science. M. Weber introduced into administrative management's development the theory of ideal bureaucracy; F. Taylor – the theory of scientific management, which became one of administrative management's schools; A. Fayol – developed the concept of company's efficiency and established a school of classical management, which presented a list of basic management functions that are basic in management.

Unsolved aspects of the problem

For a clear understanding, it is proposed to define the terms "management" and "administrative management". Consequently, "management" is a concept which means a process, or a type of activity, which is based on planning, organizing, motivating, controlling and regulating the processes of an enterprise's activity. The main and final goal of each stage is to achieve consistency between human and material resources in order to achieve the economic effect.

The term "administrative management" is a type or direction of management that studies the strategy of carrying out administrative actions in the field of enterprise management.

The main part

Very often the term "administration" is identified with the notion of public administration, the development of managerial processes in public institutions, in contrast to management, the scope of which concerns enterprise management, according to the interpretation of the American School of Management.

In essence, the administration system includes three components:

1) its theoretical foundations: the foundations of administration, the essence of the governing bodies, the role of manager in this system, as well as the main emphasis on the organization of management enterprise administrative apparatus' work.

2) management technologies (administration technologies), which mean planning and organizing business processes, as well as coordinating activities at all levels of management, motivating employees, controlling and regulating (where control management or control management matters are important). The above-mentioned technologies are the basic functions of administrative management.

Today, with the development of society, the newest technologies of administration become of great importance. A striking example of this is the formation of techniques for conducting business negotiations, business contacts, building contacts with subordinates and the technique of conducting such negotiations. As for work with subordinates, this type of management is extremely important, because the quality of personnel depends on the implementation of enterprise's main tasks.

3) managerial decisions and methods of their implementation in administrative management. It means the allocation of managerial decisions, the formation of approaches to decision-making and the rationale for the decisions made. Equally important is the information in management activities, its reliability, accuracy and efficiency.

Development mechanisms are a kind of interconnected elements and tools that are selected or determined by separate methods to achieve enterprise's goals. Usually, the notion of "mechanism" is a clear and concrete direction of subject's efforts to achieve the final result (fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Scheme of influence of administrative management's means on separate methods for the purpose of making managerial decisions

Source: Compiled by the author on materials [2-4]

The administrative management at the enterprise is designed to improve the company's activity, reduce the complexity by organizing organizational moments by administrative forms of management, in particular:

- during strategic management – the choice of clear business development strategies and possible alternatives;
- during the operational or current management the main tasks are the fulfillment of normative current tasks: production, financial, logistic, marketing, marketing, etc.;
- during the management of personnel, the formation of clear instructions: the formation of qualification requirements, the choice of methods for training employees, evaluation and payment of employees, the formation of social protection and insurance for them, as well as proper working conditions.

The main objective of administrative management's development mechanisms is to expand existing opportunities through the intensive use of current resources. The desire to improve the current system of administrative management of the enterprise and to introduce modern technologies (saving production, automated control system, quality management system, process approach, etc.), requires a sufficiently consistent procedure. Stages of realization of such steps can be represented by a generalization diagram (fig. 2) [5].

Fig. 2. The main stages of improvement of enterprise's administrative management system functioning

Source: Compiled by the author on materials [5]

Conclusions

Thus, continuous improvement on the basis of the experience gained, can develop for the enterprise the desire for self-education and development. After all, not only time (that is, the age of the enterprise in the market) is an indicator of success, and also include indicators of its effective functioning. In addition, a successful enterprise creates conditions for adapting to the environment not only for itself but for others as well as gaining its leading position. Taking into account that the main mission of administrative management consists in the bureaucratic processes of organization's registration, formation of constituent documents and registration of economic activity's subject, as well as in the formation of normative documents at the conclusion of the contract, the employer – an employee with due observance of all procedures. For the development of the administration system, attention should be paid to the most important aspects, in particular, the solution of issues related to the assessment and development of personnel at the enterprise, the improvement of enterprise's operation through the development and application of operational and regulatory levers, as well as a clear division of powers by monitoring the tasks' implementation.

Abstract

The modern development of administrative management is based on the theory of administration, quantitative methods, human behavior and management science. The theory of scientific management, which has become one of administrative management's schools and the concept of enterprise's efficiency, launched by the school of classical management form a list of basic management functions that are basic in management.

The main and final goal of each management stages – to achieve consistency between human and material resources to achieve the economic effect. The components of the administration system are determined.

The mechanism of administrative management development is highlighted and the influence of administrative management tools on its separate methods for the purpose of making managerial decisions is explored. The stages of improving the functioning of administrative management are investigated. The main objective of the mechanisms of administrative management's development is recognized expansion of existing opportunities through the intensive use of current resources.

JEL Classification: M00, M1.

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